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Impact of Climate-Smart and Water-Saving Frontier Agriculture on the WEFE Nexus in Arid Mediterranean Regions

Practice Abstract Insect Farming "How to produce *Galleria mellonella* in a small-scale insect farm"

Responsible Partner

DIPARTIMENTO DI SCIENZE AGRARIE

Authors: Elisa Appolloni, Agata Morelli, Santolo Francati, Caterina Peri, Francesco Orsini, Maria Luisa Dindo

Dissemination Level

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C	Confidential, only for members of the consortium and the Commission Services	<input type="checkbox"/>

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Introduction

The production and consumption of insects as human food or as livestock feed is considered a resource capable of having a positive impact on food security and the environment. From the perspective of human consumption, entomophagy has a long history of application. The FAO (Food and Agriculture Organization) of United Nations has estimated that there are currently two billion people in the world who practice entomophagy, especially in Asia, Africa and Latin America (especially in Mexico), being an important and cheap source of carbohydrates, proteins, fats, minerals and vitamins., insects represent a nutritious and low-environmental impact feed source obtainable from production wastes.

Insect farming requires low production inputs therefore representing an important opportunity, given the prospect of a growing world population and a simultaneous reduction in available resources. In Europe, being a so-called "Novel Food" (Regulation (EU) 2015/2283), legislation to regulate the production and consumption of insects, both for human and animal diet, has been taking first steps in recent years. At this current stage, human and animal consumption of some insect species has been approved by the European Commission, opening to a promising future increase of consumption.

Galleria mellonella (L.) (Lepidoptera Pyralidae), also known as the honey worm, is a moth whose larvae in nature usually dig tunnels in the honeycombs of the domestic bee, feeding on honey and wax. For this reason, it can become harmful by determining serious economic losses to beekeepers. However, this species also has potential from the point of view of animal nutrition. If until now *G. mellonella* larvae have often been sold as baits for sport fishing or for feeding insectivorous pets, being particularly rich in fat they could represent a useful supplement for livestock production. Depending on the case (e.g., pets, aquaculture, poultry, ruminants, pigs), in Europe these larvae could be used either alive or dried, whole or in flour or as an extract of proteins and fats. Furthermore, although it is not officially approved as an edible species for human consumption in many countries, it was found to be among the most palatable and appreciated insect during exploratory analyses.

Problem or challenge addressed

As mentioned, the world is facing a crisis related to increasing population growth and resource limitations, which will only worsen in future years. The demand for animal proteins is certainly a major obstacle to food security on the planet, considering that the use of soil for the production of feed already occupies a large part of world cultivable surface, requiring high cultivation inputs. On the contrary, the production of insects as a source of fats and proteins requires a limited demand for inputs, especially in terms of water, as it is also possible to feed them with vegetable wastes. Moreover, as regards *G. mellonella*, no added water proved to be necessary to feed the larvae.

The production of *Galleria mellonella* could be implemented on both a large and small scale, as feed for animal production (e.g., fish) or, in countries that allow it, for human consumption (subject to

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evaluation of endemicity and therefore non-dangerousness of the species for local environment, as well as of risk for human health). Being an innovative product, the production of this insect for commercial purposes still has ample room for improvement and research, especially linked to reducing the cost of the diet. However, the description of optimal rearing practices remains fundamental to ensure adequate and healthy production. The parameters and phases necessary for rearing will be described in the paragraph below

Solution / Innovation

The optimal solution for *G. mellonella* I rearing is a climatic chamber or incubator (Fig.1) that could keep a temperature of 30-32°C, a humidity relative equal to 60-70% and a photoperiod 0:24 (total dark), close to the conditions usually occurring in a beehive. However, other situations capable of resembling such conditions could be tested for homemade productions.

Fig 1. Incubator for *Galleria mellonella* rearing

Egg production is carried out by placing numerous pupae in non-toxic plastic boxes measuring 24 x 17x 9 cm. The cover has a hole where a disk of filter paper is fixed using adhesive tape. After 8-10 days, the pupae let adults emerge and they mate. After mating, the females begin to lay eggs on the paper disk, around the perimeter of the box hole (Fig. 2).

Fig 2. Paper disc with laid eggs.

The females have a high fecundity, which reaches a maximum of 1400 eggs, characterized by a high hatching rate. Every two days the paper disks with eggs are collected. They are partly used for the maintenance of the rearing and in part stored in the refrigerator at 4°C (for up to 1 month) to constitute a reserve of eggs to be used in emergency cases.

Larvae production proceeds as follows. On the bottom of non-toxic and resistant plastic boxes (*Galleria* larva can eat some kind of thin plastics), sterilized corn flour (heat at 100°C for 2-3 hours), useful for absorbing humidity, is distributed. Boxes are previously disinfected with hypochlorite solution 4%. A small portion of artificial diet (described below) is then distributed on the floor and, on top of it, part of the disk with eggs is placed. Starting from the hatching of the eggs, which occurs 7-9 days after their deposition, it is necessary to administer the diet every two days.

Given that larval development is characterized by marked asynchrony, the larvae reach maturity in 25-30 days. The mature larvae spin a white cocoon which mostly attaches to the box walls. Inside the cocoon the larvae pupate and then emerged adults start over the life cycle again. The larvae destined for consumption have to be collected before pupation, from the 20th to the 30th day after the placement of eggs on the substrate. Depending on type of consumption the larvae could be sold alive within few days or dried and transformed in powder.

Fig 3. Larvae of *Galleria mellonella* produced in plastic boxes.

Implementation (hands-on, a bit like a cooking recipe)

The optimal diet for rearing *Galleria mellonella* involves the use of expensive raw materials (such as honey or bee-wax). However, research has shown that mass rearing of the insect can also be carried out with wax-free diets or substituting some ingredients with less expensive ones (indeed the insect can eat many different wastes), thus significantly reducing costs. Research is expected to intensify on the topic of alternative diets in the next future. Below are the ingredients and method of producing an optimal diet.

The artificial diet consists of a mixture based on:

- 1000 g of corn flour,
- 1000 g of wholemeal flour,
- 2000 g of white flour,
- 1000 g of powdered milk,
- 500 g of freeze-dried yeast,
- 900 g of solid beeswax,
- 1000 g of liquid glycerin,
- 2000 g of honey.

All constituents must be heated at 100°C for 2-3 hours. The flours are placed in a mixer started at low speed and then proceed with adding the other ingredients. Subsequently, the speed of the mixer is increased to reach a good speed, mixing everything in a few minutes. The resulting mash is poured into a plastic tray, spread out and divided in small portions, which harden after about a couple of hours. Finally, the cubes obtained from the diet are fragmented into fine chips (Fig. 4) using an electric chopper. It is necessary to supply the diet every two days, providing a quantity sufficient to create on the bottom of the box a uniform layer of thickness varying from 1 to 2 cm depending on the larvae stage of development.

Fig 4. Chips of *Galleria mellonella* diet.

Tips and Hints

Although human consumption of *Galleria mellonella* is not currently officially approved in many countries, palatability evaluation studies have demonstrated a high level of liking for this insect. Below are some recipes for serving the insect (Fig. 5).

Recipe 1:

1) Ingredients:

- Toasted bread
- Galleria mellonella* cooked in the oven
- Caciocavallo DOP cheese
- Pepper jam

Recipe 2:

2) Ingredients:

- Fried *Galleria mellonella*

Recipe 3:

3) Ingredients:

- Hazelnut cream
- Almond flakes
- Galleria mellonella*
- Strawberries
- Melted dark chocolate

Recipes created by Caterina Peri, October 2015, Bologna, Italy

Fig 6. Picture of the Recipe 1 (left), Recipe 2 (centre) and Recipe 3 (right).

Links to more information (when available)

https://ipiff.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/Folder-IPIFF_Guide_A4_19.02.2024_black-colour.pdf

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